

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

Yoqubov Bobur
Umida Abdullayeva

**O'zbekiston Davlat Jahon tillari universiteti xorijiy til va adabiyoti
(Ingliz tili) 4-kurs talabasi**

**UzSWLU, Senior teacherumidaabdullayeva1985@mail.ru +998 88 788 20 70. Professor
of UzSWLU, Doctor of Philological Sciences (DSc)
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Abstract: This article discusses the teaching methods of foreign languages, the role of innovative technologies in foreign language teaching, and their importance today.

Key words: foreign language, teaching, methodology, experience, opportunity, integration, practical training.

Innovative technologies in foreign language teaching are important in facilitating learning methods and enhancing students' understanding. These technologies help to increase motivation for students, make the learning process more interesting and receive news. For example, the process of learning a foreign language can be made more convenient through online platforms, mobile applications, interactive textbooks and other innovative methods. These technologies allow users to provide and acquire education in a personalized way. Through these, students will have the opportunity to master their time and development. Innovative technologies play a crucial role in foreign language teaching by providing new and effective ways to learn languages. Here are some key conclusions about the role of innovative technologies in this field:

1. **Accessibility:** Innovative technologies make foreign language learning more accessible to a wider audience. Online platforms, language learning apps, and virtual classrooms allow learners to study languages from anywhere in the world.
2. **Personalization:** Technology enables personalized learning experiences tailored to individual needs and preferences. Adaptive learning platforms can adjust the pace and content of lessons based on the learner's progress and performance.
3. **Engagement:** Interactive tools such as language learning games, virtual reality simulations, and multimedia resources enhance learner engagement and motivation. These technologies make the learning process more enjoyable and effective.
4. **Collaboration:** Online communication tools and social media platforms facilitate collaboration among learners and teachers from different parts of the world. This fosters a sense of community and provides opportunities for authentic language practice.
5. **Feedback and Assessment:** Technology allows for immediate feedback on language exercises and assessments, helping learners track their progress and identify areas for improvement. Automated grading systems can also save time for teachers and provide consistent evaluation criteria.
6. **Cultural Understanding:** Virtual cultural experiences, online resources, and multimedia content help learners develop a deeper understanding of the culture associated with the language they are studying. This enhances their overall language proficiency and intercultural competence.

7. Lifelong Learning: Innovative technologies support lifelong language learning by offering continuous access to resources, updates, and opportunities for skill development. Learners can engage with language learning activities at their own pace and convenience.

Innovative technologies play a key role in teaching foreign languages, simplifying the learning process and increasing the effectiveness of learning. Modern online platforms, mobile applications, virtual classes and other innovative methods allow students to learn a foreign language at any convenient time and anywhere. The use of interactive learning materials, game elements, audio and video materials also contributes to more effective memorization and understanding of the language. Technologies expand learning opportunities, making it more interesting and accessible to all categories of students. Thanks to innovative technologies, students can develop speaking, listening, reading and writing skills in a foreign language more effectively and independently. Thus, innovations in the field of foreign language teaching help students achieve better results and master a new language more quickly.

Today, the importance of learning foreign languages is great. With the era of globalization, international cooperation and changes in communication systems, knowledge of foreign languages is becoming necessary. Learning foreign languages expands people's worldview, opens up new opportunities and helps to work on international relations. Knowing foreign languages changes a person's common work routine and opens up more job opportunities. Learning foreign languages gives people the opportunity to participate in global communication systems, change the international work order, and gain knowledge and experience in various fields. This allows people to use new approaches and opportunities around the world. Learning foreign languages helps people to get acquainted with new cultures and ideas, and to accept unchanging ideas and thoughts. This expands people's worldview and helps them feel their place and role in the global society. People who learn foreign languages in the society will be important for the construction and development of the global society. This helps to develop global cooperation and communication systems and strengthens people's relationships around the world.

Overall, innovative technologies have revolutionized foreign language teaching by making it more engaging, accessible, personalized, and culturally enriching. Embracing these technologies can enhance the language learning experience and empower learners to achieve their language proficiency goals effectively.

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